

Medium and High-Level Digital Skills in DESI Countries

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They grew by 15.04% between 2016 and 2021

The DESI Index calculates the value of people who have digital skills above the basic level in the following sectors, namely: information, communication, problem solving and software for creating content.

Ranking of countries by value of people with digital skills above basic level in DESI countries. Finland ranks first for the value of the presence of people with basic digital skills with a value of 18.97 units, followed by the Netherlands with a value of 18.77 units and Denmark with a value of 18.38 units. In the middle of the table there are Ireland with a value of 12.93 units, followed by Lithuania with a value of 12.23 units and Portugal with a value of 12.16 units. Poland closes the ranking with a value of 8.06 units, followed by Bulgaria for a value of 4.28 units and Romania with a value of 3.91 units. On average in 2021 the value of people with digital skills above basic ones was equal to a value of 12.14.

Ranking of DESI countries by percentage change in the value of people with digital skills above the basic level in the period 2016 and 2021. Cyprus ranks first in terms of value of the change in the percentage of people with digital skills above the basic level with an amount equal to 64.31% equal to an amount of 3.74 units, followed by Greece with a value of 44.81% equal to an amount of 2.73 units, and by Poland with a value equal to 41.32% equal to an amount of 2.36 units. In the middle of the table there are France with a value equal to 15.16% equal to an amount of 1.54 units, followed by Portugal with a value of 15.14% equal to an amount of 1.6 units and Romania with a value equal to 15.14% equal to an amount of 0.51 units. Estonia closes the ranking with a value equal to -1.10% equal to an amount of -0.16 units, followed by Latvia with an amount of -4.26% equal to an amount of -0.41 units and from Bulgaria with a value equal to -11.46% equal to an amount of -0.55 units.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. The analysis shows the presence of four clusters made up as indicated below:

- Cluster 1: Luxembourg, Croatia, Spain, Belgium, Lithuania, Portugal, Austria, Estonia, Germany, Malta, Slovakia, France, Slovenia, Ireland;
- Cluster 2: Greece, Italy, Poland, Czech Republic, Cyprus, Hungary, Latvia;
- Cluster 3: Netherlands, Finland, Denmark, Sweden;
- Cluster 4: Romania, Bulgaria.

It follows that from the point of view of metrics it appears that the median value of Cluster 3-C3 is equal to an amount of 18.576, while the median value of Cluster 1-C1 is equal to an amount of 13.16 units, Cluster 2 -C2 is equal to an amount of 9.26 units, while the value of Cluster 4-C4 is equal to an amount of 4.09 units. The ordering of the clusters is shown below: C3> C1> C2> C4. From a strictly geographical point of view, the presence of a dominance of the Scandinavian countries and in general

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of Northern Europe is evident, compared to the countries of Mediterranean Europe and Southern Europe.

Network analysis using the Manhattan distance. An analysis is presented below through the application of network analysis with the use of the Manhattan distance. The analysis shows the presence of three complex network structures. There is a complex network structure between France, Slovenia, Portugal, Lithuania, Belgium, Spain, Luxembourg, Croatia. Particularly:

- France has a connection with Slovenia with a value of 0.11 units, and with Portugal for a value of 0.2 units;
- Slovenia has a connection with France for a value of 0.11 units and with Portugal for a value of 0.22 units;
- Portugal has a connection with France for a value equal to 0.2 units, with Slovenia for a value equal to 0.22 units, and with Lithuania for a value equal to 0.23 units;
- Lithuania has a connection with Portugal for a value of 0.23 units, and with Belgium for a value of 0.25 units;
- Belgium has a connection with Lithuania for a value of 0.25 units and with Spain for a value of 0.18 units;
- Spain has a connection with Belgium for a value of 0.18 units and with Luxembourg for a value of 0.2 units;
- Luxembourg has a connection with Spain for a value of 0.2 units and with Croatia for a value of 0.16 units.

The analysis shows that the most connected country is Portugal.

There is a complex network structure consisting of Italy, Greece, and Poland. Particularly:

- Italy has a connection with Greece for a value of 0.28 units;
- Greece has a connection with Italy for a value of 0.28 and with Poland for a value of 0.17 units;
- Poland has a connection with Greece equal to an amount of 0.17 units.
- There is a complex network structure between Austria, Germany and Malta. Particularly:
- Austria has a connection with Germany for a value of 0.22 units;
- Germany has a connection with Austria for a value of 0.22 units and with Malta for a value of 0.24 units;
- Malta has a connection with Germany for a value of 0.24 units.

Conclusion. The value of people with digital skills above the basic ones has grown on average for the DESI countries by an amount equal to 15.54% between 2016 and 2021. However, there are still significant differences between the countries of Northern Europe and the countries of Southern and Eastern Europe. The network structure confirms the presence of effective links in the development of the variable especially for cluster 1 countries. The presence of people with medium-high digital skills is essential not only in the context of production but also in the consumer sector. In fact, in the current economic system, individuals are prosumers or produce and consume digital products. The growth of medium-high level digital skills can therefore significantly improve both the ability of companies to produce and also the ability of companies to offer consumers more advanced products by relying on a higher degree of market innovation on the demand side.

Competenze Digitali di Medio-Alto Livello

<i>Countries</i>	<i>2016</i>	<i>2017</i>	<i>2018</i>	<i>2019</i>	<i>2020</i>	<i>2021</i>	<i>Var Ass</i>	<i>Var Per</i>
<i>Austria</i>	☆ 12,4	☆ 13,1	★ 13,7	★ 13,7	★ 14,9	★ 14,9	☆ 2,44	★ 19,61
<i>Belgium</i>	☆ 11,8	☆ 11,9	☆ 11,7	☆ 11,7	☆ 12,9	☆ 12,9	☆ 1,16	☆ 9,80
<i>Bulgaria</i>	☆ 4,83	☆ 3,82	☆ 4,19	☆ 4,19	☆ 4,28	☆ 4,28	☆ -0,55	★ -11,46
<i>Croatia</i>	☆ 11,5	☆ 12,6	☆ 13	☆ 13	☆ 13,4	☆ 13,4	☆ 1,92	★ 16,73
<i>Cyprus</i>	☆ 5,82	☆ 7,74	☆ 7,09	☆ 7,09	☆ 9,56	☆ 9,56	☆ 3,74	★ 64,31
<i>Czechia</i>	☆ 8,69	☆ 7,73	☆ 9,11	☆ 9,11	☆ 9,77	☆ 9,77	☆ 1,09	☆ 12,50
<i>Denmark</i>	★ 18,4	★ 20,1	★ 17,9	★ 17,9	★ 18,4	★ 18,4	☆ 0,02	☆ 0,14
<i>Estonia</i>	★ 14,2	☆ 13,2	☆ 13,2	☆ 13,2	★ 14	★ 14	☆ -0,16	☆ -1,10
<i>Finland</i>	★ 15,5	★ 16,6	★ 17,1	★ 17,1	★ 19	★ 19	☆ 3,46	★ 22,31
<i>France</i>	☆ 10,2	☆ 10,4	☆ 11,1	☆ 11,1	☆ 11,7	☆ 11,7	☆ 1,54	★ 15,16
<i>Germany</i>	☆ 13,4	☆ 12,7	★ 13,9	★ 13,9	★ 14,7	★ 14,7	☆ 1,34	☆ 10,04
<i>Greece</i>	☆ 6,1	☆ 7,33	☆ 8,21	☆ 8,21	☆ 8,83	☆ 8,83	☆ 2,73	★ 44,81
<i>Hungary</i>	☆ 8,49	☆ 9,02	☆ 9,76	☆ 9,76	☆ 9,61	☆ 9,61	☆ 1,11	☆ 13,10
<i>Ireland</i>	☆ 9,47	☆ 9,39	☆ 10,5	☆ 10,5	☆ 12,9	☆ 12,9	☆ 3,46	★ 36,50
<i>Italy</i>	☆ 7,32	☆ 7,38	☆ 7,86	☆ 7,86	☆ 8,34	☆ 8,34	☆ 1,02	★ 13,97
<i>Latvia</i>	☆ 9,67	☆ 10,1	☆ 10,2	☆ 10,2	☆ 9,26	☆ 9,26	☆ -0,41	★ -4,26
<i>Lithuania</i>	☆ 11,5	☆ 11	☆ 12,1	☆ 12,1	☆ 12,2	☆ 12,2	☆ 0,76	☆ 6,64
<i>Luxembourg</i>	☆ 11,5	☆ 11,9	☆ 12,7	☆ 12,7	☆ 13,5	☆ 13,5	☆ 2,07	★ 17,99
<i>Malta</i>	☆ 13,1	☆ 12,1	★ 14,7	★ 14,7	★ 14,5	★ 14,5	☆ 1,41	☆ 10,75
<i>Netherlands</i>	★ 16,1	★ 17	★ 18,1	★ 18,1	★ 18,8	★ 18,8	☆ 2,67	★ 16,56
<i>Poland</i>	☆ 5,71	☆ 7,35	☆ 8	☆ 8	☆ 8,06	☆ 8,06	☆ 2,36	★ 41,32
<i>Portugal</i>	☆ 10,6	☆ 10,7	☆ 11,6	☆ 11,6	☆ 12,2	☆ 12,2	☆ 1,60	★ 15,14
<i>Romania</i>	☆ 3,4	☆ 3,26	☆ 3,84	☆ 3,84	☆ 3,91	☆ 3,91	☆ 0,51	★ 15,14
<i>Slovakia</i>	☆ 9,88	☆ 11	☆ 12,5	☆ 12,5	☆ 10,3	☆ 10,3	☆ 0,38	☆ 3,80
<i>Slovenia</i>	☆ 9,7	☆ 10,5	☆ 11,2	☆ 11,2	☆ 11,8	☆ 11,8	☆ 2,06	★ 21,27
<i>Spain</i>	☆ 11,4	☆ 11,6	☆ 12	☆ 12	★ 13,7	★ 13,7	☆ 2,30	★ 20,20
<i>Sweden</i>	☆ 13,3	★ 14,7	★ 17,6	★ 17,6	★ 17,4	★ 17,4	☆ 4,09	★ 30,65
<i>Media</i>	☆ 10,5	☆ 10,9	☆ 11,6	☆ 11,6	☆ 12,1	☆ 12,1	☆ 1,63	★ 15,54

Declarations

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